

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation and Service Deployment

D5.5 Report on Federated Network Studies (1)

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	European Patients’ Forum - Belgium
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene / BMS	Celgene Management SARL – Switzerland
BI	Boehringer Ingelheim International GmbH - Germany

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The objective of the EHDEN Consortium is to provide all the necessary services that enable a federated European data network to perform fast, scalable and highly reproducible research, while respecting privacy regulations, local data provenance and governance. This includes services and tools to perform data standardisation, analytical pipelines, tools to share study results, and tools for stakeholder engagement and training. The EHDEN Consortium combines active participation of stakeholder representatives with proven experience in: a) integrating different data types, methods and technologies to utilise diverse clinical datasets; b) platform development to make methods and datasets Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR); and c) engaging a wide variety of stakeholders, including health technology assessment agencies, regulators and patients.

Success of this eco-system is ultimately measured by the amount and representativeness of the data included in the network, the number and relevance of studies executed, and the science translated into regulatory pathways and real-world practice, as well as the mutual involvement of key stakeholders. Currently, EHDEN has onboarded [98 Data Partners](#) in Europe that has standardised their data to the OMOP CDM and has trained and certified a large number of [Small and Medium-sized Enterprises](#) (SMEs) to support the Data Partners with standardisation to the OMOP CDM.

This deliverable is the first in a series of three that focusses on Federated Network Studies through EHDEN. It describes the governance and operational model to execute studies based on more than a decade of experience in observational database studies. It describes all the steps in the process from research question to final results. This first version will form the basis for further improvement taking an agile approach in which we learn from each federated network study through iterative cycles.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The vision of the European Health Data and Evidence Network (EHDEN) project is to be the trusted observational research ecosystem to enable better health decisions, outcomes and care (www.ehden.eu). To realise this vision EHDEN is implementing a new paradigm for the discovery and analysis of health data in Europe by building a large-scale, federated network of data sources standardised to the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP-CDM). The OMOP-CDM is maintained by the Observational Health Data Science and Informatics (OHDSI) global initiative with which we intensively collaborate (www.ohdsi.org).

Figure 1. Requirements for a large-scale reliable evidence generation.

The core objective of the EHDEN Consortium is to provide all the necessary services that enable a sustainable distributed European data network to perform fast, scalable, and highly reproducible research, while respecting privacy regulations, local data provenance and governance. This includes services and tools to improve data interoperability through data standardisation, standardised analytical pipelines, tools to share study results and tools for stakeholder engagement and training. We will implement a technical framework and also all necessary processes for a high-quality and fully reproducible data workflow. Core to EHDEN is open science, which entails the use of open-source tools, an open federated health data network, and an engaged community that shares the EHDEN vision and mission. EHDEN will build a sustainable and trustworthy platform that will drive the generation and use of Real-World Evidence (RWE) to support decision making on any type of healthcare interventions and healthcare research with diverse longitudinal patient level health data. Although our main aim is to build the 'new operating system' for real-world health research in Europe we will ensure global interoperability through the use of the OMOP-CDM. Success of this operating system is ultimately measured by the amount and representativeness of the data included in the network, the number and relevance of studies executed and ultimately the science translated into regulatory pathways and real-world practice, as well as the mutual involvement of key stakeholders.

The role of WP5 in EHDEN is to provide guidance in the implementation of the data workflow starting from the Extraction Transformation and Load (ETL) to the OMOP-CDM all the way to the federated network studies and dissemination of the results. In the first years of the project, WP5 developed and deployed procedures for the certification of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) to support the ETL process, and procedures for the onboarding of data sources in the EHDEN data network (see D5.1, D5.3, and D5.4). In addition, WP5 focussed on Quality Control of the full data workflow as described in D5.2).

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During the project, several proof-of-concept studies were executed in the federated data network driven by the use cases in WP1-3, for example through study-a-thons in which a focused group of experts was brought together to generate reliable evidence on a specific research question pertaining to a disease domain. The study execution process was initiated, supported, and evaluated by WP5. If requested by WP1-3, a study will be initiated through an open call for participation through the OHDSI website and other channels. Guidance will be given in the development of study protocols and approvals needed. Finally, in WP5 the full study execution workflow will be evaluated, and feedback will be given to further optimise tools and processes developed by other WPs.

2. PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF DELIVERABLE

The current deliverable is the first in a series of three that focusses on Federated Network Studies through EHDEN. In this first deliverable, the focus is on the definition of requirements for the execution of these studies as a high-level blueprint. This is driving the development of most of the other WPs in EDHEN, for example the tools on WP4 Technical Infrastructure. We have not started from scratch, but build on expertise obtained from prior projects, such as the European Medical Information Framework (EMIF) project and the large number of network studies performed by OHDSI. We will start under the assumption that the network is realised, and many data sources are ready to participate in federated studies.

For this deliverable, sustainability aspects of the federated network and the business models that could be defined are out-of-scope. This discussion is driven by WP6 Outreach and Sustainability and will be described in upcoming deliverables.

EHDEN will setup a Coordination Centre that will be responsible for the operational aspect of study execution through the EHDEN Data Network. It will work as a front office for study requests and will provide support during the study workflow as we need. Based on our prior experience in multi-database study execution, the following scenarios have been identified:

1) Fully outsourced

This scenario is most common for commercial parties and regulatory bodies, but also sometimes applies to public funders like IMI or H2020. The Study Requester has a question that needs to be answered using real-world data and wants to fully outsource this to a third party (EHDEN) with minimum requirements with respect to number and type of data sources and their geographic spread. In most situations there is no protocol yet and this also needs to be developed by the team of experts that has to be formed by EHDEN. The Study Requester will provide feedback following an established governance procedure of protocol review in which the design choices are made by the third party. Regular meetings are planned to update on results and timelines.

2) Partially outsourced

We have seen a very small number of requests where a fully developed protocol is already available, for example, in a replication study. In this scenario, the EHDEN Coordination Centre would first provide feedback to assess the study design and the feasibility of the study (via a scientific advisor). This often results in modifications to the initially proposed protocol.

3) Fully engaged

This scenario is most common in an academic setting. Here the Study Requester is a full partner in the study team, may contribute data, help in study implementation and execution, and often plays a leading role in the results dissemination process. The role of EHDEN is mainly being a facilitator and providing experts for the successful execution of the study.

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The operational model this deliverable is focusing on is one in which a **stakeholder (“Study Requester”)** **wants to execute a study in the data network and has a budget available to fully outsource its execution.** This could be a pharmaceutical company, an academic organisation, a regulator, etc. Of course, other operational models and scenarios are in scope for the EHDEN Data Network, such as an open community type of study without a budget in which Data Partner could voluntarily participate to improve patient care and multiple Data Partners take responsibilities beyond contributing data. This and other complex mixes of scenarios will be worked out in more detail in the upcoming “Federated Network Studies” deliverables.

3. STUDY TYPES

Initially, the **study types** that are deemed in scope within the EHDEN project are selected based on the availability of analytical pipelines. This includes a rich set of analytics in R and tools for to execute characterisation studies, population-level effect estimation studies, and patient-level prediction studies. They are described briefly in the sections below (for more detail see The Book of OHDSI (<https://book.ohdsi.org>)). Other study types can be proposed to the EHDEN Coordination Centre and can potentially also be executed but this would impact budget requirements and study timelines. A Catalogue of Standardised Analytics is created that is expanded over time driven by new use cases.

These study types will have different **complexity levels**, but still the intention is to automate as much as possible the definition of studies, their implementation, and execution to obtain a reliable high throughput system.

3.1 Characterisation

Observational healthcare databases provide a valuable resource to understand variations in populations based on a host of characteristics. Characterising populations through the use of descriptive statistics is an important first step in generating hypotheses about the determinants of health and disease. The following types of characterisations are in scope:

- 1) **Database-level characterisation:** provides a top-level set of summary statistics to understand the profile of a database in its totality.
- 2) **Cohort characterisation:** describes a population in terms of aggregate socio-demographics, clinical measurements, medical history, undertaken procedures, and medicines use.
- 3) **Treatment pathways:** describes the sequence of interventions people in a specified population received for a given duration of time.
- 4) **Incidence:** measures the incidence rate of an outcome in a specified population for a given time at risk.

With the exception of database-level characterisation, these methods aim to describe events in a patient population relative to an event referred to as the index date, for example, the date on which a person was diagnosed with a disease. Characterisation studies therefore require a cohort, a set of persons who satisfy one or more inclusion criteria for a duration of time. In [Chapter 10](#) of the Book of OHDSI this topic is described in more detail. Use-cases for characterisation include disease natural history, treatment utilisation and quality improvement.

3.2 Population-Level Estimation

Observational healthcare data, such as administrative claims and electronic health records, offer opportunities to generate real-world evidence about the effect of treatments that can meaningfully improve the lives of patients. Population-level effect estimation refers to the estimation of average causal effects of

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exposures (e.g. medical interventions such as drug exposures or procedures) on specific health outcomes of interest. In what follows, we consider two different estimation tasks:

- **Direct effect estimation:** estimating the effect of an exposure on the risk of an outcome or set of outcomes, as compared to no exposure.
- **Comparative effect estimation:** estimating the effect of an exposure (the target exposure) on the risk of an outcome, as compared to another exposure (the comparator exposure).

In both cases, the patient-level causal effect contrasts a factual outcome, i.e., what happened to the exposed patient, with a counterfactual outcome, i.e., what would have happened had the exposure not occurred (direct) or had a different exposure occurred (comparative). Since any one patient reveals only the factual outcome (the fundamental problem of causal inference), the various effect estimation designs employ different analytic devices to shed light on the counterfactual outcomes.

Use-cases for population-level effect estimation include treatment selection, safety surveillance, and comparative effectiveness. Methods can test specific hypotheses one at a time (e.g. ‘signal evaluation’) or explore multiple-hypotheses-at-once (e.g. ‘signal detection’). In all cases, the objective remains the same: to produce as accurate and precise an estimate of the causal effect as possible.

3.3 Patient-Level Prediction

Large-scale, patient-specific predictive modelling has become reality thanks to the large data network in which the Common Data Model (CDM) allows for uniform and transparent analysis at an unprecedented scale. The growing network of databases standardized to the CDM enables external validation of models in different healthcare settings on a global level. We believe this provides immediate opportunity to serve large communities of patients who are in most need of improved quality of care. Such models can inform truly personalised medical care, leading, hopefully, to sharply improved patient outcomes.

In Patient-Level Prediction (PLP) we aim to predict among a population at risk which patients at a defined moment in time will experience some outcome during a time-at-risk. Prediction is done using only information about the patients in an observation window prior to that moment in time. The framework developed enforces best practices for the development and validation of the prediction model and can be applied for all types of prediction problems, e.g. disease onset and progression, treatment choice, treatment response, treatment safety, treatment adherence.

4. STUDY PROCESS STEPS

In this chapter we will discuss all the necessary steps in the study process. We can distinguish an exploration, negotiation, implementation, execution, and dissemination phase that each has sub steps. This applies to the context of a Study Requester that has a budget and wants to fully outsource the execution of a study to the EHDEN Coordination Centre. For other scenarios, parts of this pipeline may apply, e.g., in the case of a voluntary study no budget agreements are needed.

Figure 2. High-level overview of the proposed study execution process in the EHDEN Data Network.

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Phase	Description
Exploration	Consists of the study proposal step, the engagement with the data network to allow them to express interest to consider participations, a feasibility step with respect to data and resources for the requested services through interaction with the Core teams.
Negotiation	Involves the agreement on budgets with all involved partners using a Responsibility Assignment Matrix (RAM) driven by the requested services. Furthermore, contracts need to be agreed upon with the involved institutions
Implementation	Includes protocol development, update and quality control steps of data sources if necessary, governance approval, analytical pipeline development.
Execution	Consists of the distribution of the study code to the Data Partners and iterative cycle of quality control. This may require additional updates on the study implementation.
Dissemination	Includes results dashboards, study report(s), publication(s). For each an approval workflow is established with the relevant stakeholders.

In the sections below each phase of the process is explained in more detail.

4.1 Exploration

In the exploration phase, the Study Requester is interacting with the Coordination Centre to explore the feasibility of the study with respect to the available data and resources within the budget constraints. This starts with a study proposal, followed by engagement with the Operations Board and the Data Network. This exploration phase will result in a decision approved by the Operations Board to enter the negotiation phase or not.

4.1.1 Study proposal

The Study Requester has to inform the EHDEN Coordination Centre about the proposed study using a formalised process:

- 1) The Study Requester fills in a Study Proposal Form (see Appendix 1.) and submits this to the Coordination Centre. The form describes the study objectives, study design, requested number, type and geographic spread of data sources, proposed list of data sources if known, the timelines, and an indicative budget. The PMO is first line of contact to support the Study Requester in this process.
- 2) The Coordination Centre performs a first eligibility check, informs the Study Requester about the need for additional clarification, and finally sends the Study Proposal Form to a Scientific Advisor (or the full Scientific Advisory Board). The SAB will assess the feasibility of the requested services.

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- 3) The SAB will review the form and additional shared information and will provide feedback on the study design using a Project Review Template. The Project Management Office will inform the Requester and an alignment process is started on the study design.

4.1.2 Operations Board Review

The proposal will be assessed by EHDEN to provide an indication of the required resources to implement and execute the study from an analytical, data, technical, and epidemiological standpoint, in collaboration with the PMO. The EHDEN Database Catalogue is a valuable resource to assess suitability of data sources for a particular purpose. The available data domains in the data source of the Data Partners can provide guidance on the feasibility of a study, e.g. studies requiring genetics, omics, mobile data are most probably out-of-scope at the current stage since these are not captured in the current version of the OMOP-CDM (see <https://ohdsi.github.io/CommonDataModel/>). For example, in Figure 3 below the available data domains are shown in the Dutch Integrated Primary Care Information (IPCI) Database (www.ipci.org). This information would be helpful to see that this particular database has unstructured information, Drug Exposure records etc.

Database-Level Dashboard

Figure 3. Interactive Database-Level Dashboard of the available data domains in the Integrated Primary Care Information (IPCI) data base.

The Database Dashboard also provides insights into the available data on a concept level, for example how many Diabetes records are in the database.

4.1.3 Data Network Engagement

Once the Study Proposal Triage has been finalised and the study is taken under consideration, it will be time to engage with the Data Network. The following options are suggested:

- 1) If the Study Requester and the initial feasibility assessment have defined a list of specific potential data sources, these will be informed about the proposed study. If the SAB has suggested additional data sources these will also be contacted if agreed with the Study Requester.
- 2) If the Study Requester needs a broader overview of the available data sources, the Coordination Centre can broadcast the proposal to all that are in scope considering the request data types,

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geographic spread, etc. This process step requires some discussion since a limited budget means that a limited number of data sources can be included in the study.

- 3) Unless the Study needs to be executed under Non-Disclosure Agreement, each study will be publicly communicated through the EHDEN website if this is in line with the expectations of the Study Requester.

The Data Partners will be asked to provide feedback to the request and to express interest in the study within a predefined timeframe. Additional feasibility checks may be necessary at this step; however, for certain studies this would only be possible at a later stage which may require clauses in the contract with the Data Partner. There is no obligation for a Data Partner to participate in a study but also no guarantee they will be included in every study even if they are interested and complete feasibility checks.

The final selection of Data Partners proposed to participate in the study will be done by the Operations Board together with the Study Requester. This may include a first tier of Data Partners that are essential, and a second tier of Data Partners whose participation will depend on budget availability or other factors (e.g. study interim results, introduction of specific products on specific national markets, etc.).

4.2 Negotiation

The negotiation phase involves the agreement on requested services, team formation, budget, and the contractual agreements with the involved institutions.

4.2.1 Service Agreement

Based on the advice provided by the Operations board, an agreement is reached with the Study Requester on the services that will be provided and the timelines. This forms the basis for the contractual agreements and needs to be signed off by the PI and the Operations Board.

4.2.2 Team formation

A Study Team is proposed consisting of members of the Operations Core teams and the team of the Study Requester if applicable. A typical team consists of members with roles and responsibilities as described in Table 1,

Table 1. Study team roles and responsibilities

Role	Description
(Co)-Principal Investigator(s)	Senior oversight and assumes responsibility for study design and scientific co-ordination of the project
Senior Project Manager	Owns project management (study conduct, management of inputs from multiple experts and consultants; primary contact; QC; budget)
Senior Epidemiologist/Statistician	Senior review/QC of all deliverables; expertise for advice on study design, protocols, interpretation and reporting
Data Scientist	Owns programming of the analytical pipeline
Data Steward	Owns the execution of the study, collection of the results, and the quality monitoring of the results.
Data Custodian(s)	Own site-level execution of study package and results consolidation for synthesis into deliverables. Contribute local database expertise.
Advisory Group Member(s)	Provide scientific and or ethical advice as needed.

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According to ENCePP guidelines and Code of Conduct, a full disclosure of any conflicts of interest will be required for any PI(s) contributing to the leadership of a study using Annex 5 of the Code of Conduct.

Note that the roles described above can be taken by members of the EHDEN Coordination Centre, but also by others from the participating institutions. For example, the Principal Investigator could come from one of the participating institutions. This rotating principal investigator-ship can be decided upon based on expertise on the study topic, availability of resources, etc.

4.2.2 Budget Agreement

An agreement is reached with all involved partners and Study Requester using a Responsibility Assignment Matrix (RAM) driven by the requested services and the input from the Operations Board evaluation. Budget agreements could start with a predefined indication of costs based on different study types.

4.2.3 Contractual Agreements

If the proposal is accepted, a contract will be signed with the Study Requester. Derived contracts with participating institutions will also be arranged. All contractual arrangements will be standardised and pre-negotiated as much as possible to streamline this process via quicker legal clearance, especially with Data Partners.

4.3 Implementation

The implementation of the study requires several sequential steps that often include multiple iterative cycles. At the core is the protocol that transparently describes how the study has to be implemented. This protocol has to be approved by the governance board of each participating Data Partner. In some studies, additional steps have to be taken locally, for example, to update the CDM. Furthermore, a study package has to be developed that can be executed against the CDM and tools may have to be developed to disseminate the results.

4.3.1 Protocol Development

In most situations a study protocol is not yet available when the study request is received and EHDEN will be asked to develop the protocol as a service. This service will then have to be provided by the Epidemiology Core as part of the contract. If the Study Requester has a predefined protocol this will require review and a feedback round. In both situations the protocol will have to be developed following the [ENCePP code of conduct](#) from which the first section is added here for convenience:

“The protocol shall be developed before the study commences by individuals with appropriate scientific background and experience, taking into account the elements of the ENCePP checklist for Study Protocols.

The protocol must be designed to ensure scientifically valid and sound results are generated independently from any potential conflicting interest of the funder or the researcher. To achieve this aim, the protocol needs to pre-define certain information before the study starts, as outlined in the ENCePP checklist for Study Protocols, including a timetable for the progress and completion of the study and describing milestones (e.g. interim reports) and deadlines. Feasibility studies that were carried out in advance, if any, should be described in the protocol. Feasibility studies should not include pre-analyses of data which indicate the likely direction of the results and such studies prior to protocol finalisation would invalidate ENCePP Study status.

Any amendments or updates to the protocol after the study start should be documented in a traceable and auditable way including the dates of the changes. Changes to the protocol that may affect the

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interpretation of the study shall be identifiable and reported as such in publications and in the publicly available register where the study is included, and should be considered when interpreting the findings. This includes additions or amendments to the objectives or endpoints after the study start. An explanation for the change(s) to the protocol should be recorded with the protocol alterations or provided upon request once the study results have been published.”

Protocol development is often the most time-consuming phase in an observational study since all foreseen analysis must be described up front. This requires intense interaction in the study team and with the Study Requester. However, template protocols tuned to a specific research question could considerably improve the speed of this process. EHDEN has performed work on this as described in D1.2 “Final study protocol for proposed proof-of-concept studies”, and also OHDSI has created protocol examples that could be used to create study protocol template.

The protocol will be registered in the EU PAS register.

4.3.2 Governance Approval

Protocol approval at the study sites is necessary not only with regard to the research question itself but also to comply with the local implementation of relevant laws and directives in the various European states, in particular the GDPR and DGA. This regulation is about the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data. These approvals are part of the safeguards that different controllers have installed to comply with the national implementation of this regulation. Each data custodian is responsible for protocol approval from their local governance board prior to study execution. For a non-interventional observational study, there may be no need for ethical approval in certain data sources.

This process has proven to be time consuming in the past since it depends on individual governance boards with different requirements, visions, and timelines. EHDEN could assess the procedures at each site in anticipation and take an active role in alignment where possible. The EHDEN Database Catalogue is a good start since it has a section that describes the governance procedure for each data source in the data network. However, if possible we will seek agreement on standardised studies and protocol templates with at least a subset of the Data Partners, e.g. for drug utilisation studies, that can be assessed in a more expedited way by the local governance board. We do need to manage expectations, since this is not under the control of EHDEN.

4.3.3 Data Source Onboarding

In this deliverable we assume that the data source has already been mapped to the OMOP-CDM when participating in the network study so an Extraction Transform Load (ETL) development step will not be discussed. However, we do want to execute quality control procedures prior to each study execution. These are described in detail in [D5.2 Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures](#). Briefly, for each data source the Data Quality Dashboard and CDM Inspection R packages will be executed and checked. If necessary, changes will be made in the ETL. Furthermore, a data source refresh may be required to obtain the most recent data in the CDM or an update of the standardised vocabularies.

4.3.4 Analysis Implementation

For each study the analysis needs to be implemented as an R package that can be executed by the Data Partner against the CDM. This task is performed by a Data Scientist or Statistician from the Analytics Core Team. Where possible already existing packages are re-used to increase both efficiency and validity of programming and study execution.

As described in [The Book of OHDSI](#) there are different ways to implement a study (see Figure 4).

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Figure 4. Different ways to implement a study

A study can be designed using the ATLAS tool and downloaded as an R Package, e.g., for patient-level prediction. This R Package can then be further adapted if necessary. A second option is to implement an analysis using the [Health Analytics Data-to-Evidence Suite](#) (HADES) methods library, a set of open-source R packages for large scale analytics, including population characterization, population-level causal effect estimation, and patient-level prediction. HADES contains many supportive R packages that can be used in custom studies, such as DatabaseConnector and SqlRender. The third option is to build completely custom analyses leveraging the full power of R (or any other programming language). This provides the maximum flexibility, and may in fact be the only option if the specific analysis is not supported by any of our tools. However, this path requires a lot of technical skills, time, and effort, and as the analysis increases in complexity it becomes harder to avoid errors in the code. For any implementation, the Software Validity process as described in [D5.2 Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures](#) applies including unit testing, regression testing, and acceptance testing. All study packages are version controlled and in principle made publicly available for transparency.

4.3.5 Cohort Diagnostics

An important step in each analysis is to define proper phenotypes for the target and outcome cohorts that work across the included data sources. This requires the use of the [Cohort Diagnostics R package](#) that provides an in-depth characterisation of the phenotype definitions, secular trends over time, standard as well as orphan source codes (not included source codes that may be of interest), and cohort participant/s characterisation. The results can be visualised in a web application as shown in Figure 5 below. Often multiple iterations of the phenotype definitions are made before the final set is included in the Study R Package.

Figure 5. Cohort Diagnostics Application

To improve the efficiency of this step work is ongoing to develop a [Phenotype Library](#), an open community resource maintained by the OHDSI community to support phenotype development, evaluation, sharing and re-use.

4.3.5 Test Runs

Before study initiation the analytics are tested on a subset of the data sources or on a simulated set of patients. Once all the tests are passed the package is released for execution against all the participating data sources.

4.4 Execution

4.4.1 Study Initiation

Before study execution, a meeting will be organised by the PMO that includes all the Data Partners, the Principal Investigator, and the persons responsible for the development of the analytics. In the meeting timelines are agreed and communication channels are established for support during the execution phase. Ideally, the study is prepared in Arachne to optimally control and monitor the study execution (more details on Arachne will be made available in upcoming WP4 deliverables).

4.4.2 Execution Iterations

The Data Partner locally executes the analytics against the CDM and reviews the results before returning them to the study coordinator (via Arachne). Sometimes multiple execution iterations are performed and additional fine tuning of the code base is needed. The Data Core team members are the first line of contact for Data Partners during the study execution and will inform the PMO on the progress made.

4.4.3 Results Collection

The final results of all data sources are collected and checked by the Data Core and Analytics Core team members. Once these are approved the Dissemination Step is initiated.

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4.5 Dissemination

4.5.1 Results Composition

The results of all the data sources are combined to produce the tables and figures needed for the report or publication. The pooling of database-specific results will be pre-specified per protocol, including rules/diagnostics precluding the inclusion of a database and the use of meta-analytic approaches to combine data-specific estimates. This sometimes requires some code development by the Statistician and/or Epidemiologist. The results are reviewed by the Epidemiology members of the team and conclusions are formed. If requested as a service, the SAB can review the study results prior to the development of the manuscript.

4.5.2 Dashboard Instantiation

In most studies executed against the CDM, a large amount of study results is generated for many data sources. Therefore, dashboards in the form of a web application are made to make it easier to study all these results. In most standardised analytical pipelines these web applications already exist and can be re-used. All the uploaded study results can be easily combined in a single folder from which the dashboard is instantiated. The web application can be made publicly available or if necessary can be made available behind a security layer.

4.5.3 Reporting

If requested as a service, the team can prepare (interim) reports and manuscripts for publication. All study reports will be written in accordance with the GVP guidelines module VIII, (EMA/813938/2011) and the 2010 EU pharmacovigilance legislation (Articles 10 or 10a of Regulation (EC) No 726/2004; Articles 21a or 22a of Directive 2001/83/EC). Updates to the study protocol in case of substantial amendments, progress reports where applicable, and the final study report will be entered in the ENCePP EU PAS register if applicable.

Study findings will preferably be considered for publication as open access (to be discussed with the Study Requester). Co-authorship for the publication will be guided by the Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals: Writing and Editing for Biomedical Publication of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE). In addition, affiliations and conflicts of interest shall be disclosed. The lead author shall accept responsibility for the overall content of the study publication and the accuracy and integrity of the data presented as well as for any conclusions drawn from the data.

5. NEXT STEPS

The current version of the Study Execution Workflow has already proven its value. It is now applied actively for studies using the OMOP CDM. This also includes recent studies for the European Medicines Agency, e.g., a drug utilisation study on Ranitidine and other Histamine-H₂-Receptor Antagonists [[EUPASS33397](#)]. This study could have been fully executed in just a few months due to all the efficiency steps that were made using the CDM and standardised analytics. The most time-consuming step was the protocol development.

Refinements based on additional use cases could further improve the efficiency of the workflow. In close collaboration with WP1, WP2, WP3 the set of standardised analytics and protocol templates will be further extended through high impact use cases. Furthermore, we formed an Evidence Taskforce to drive study execution of studies within the growing EHDEN data network. This includes unfunded studies driven by the community, which will require an adjustment of the current workflow. The use cases will also drive the agile development of the technical framework led by WP4, e.g., operationalisation of the Database Catalogue, the analytical tools, and the setup of a service desk to support the actors.

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Finally, EHDEN is in the process of setting up a not-for-profit organisation to further operationalise and sustain the workflow at scale. The current deliverable provides an important blueprint for the execution of studies by this organisation.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 Study Request Form

Question	Details
Name	
Email	
Organisation	
Address	
Phone number	
Describe your expertise on OMOP-CDM and the execution of federated studies in the EHDEN/OHDSI data network	
Describe if data sources from your own organisation will participate and if they are already in the OMOP-CDM format	
Provide a short description of the study	
Rationale for the study	
Specify your Study Objectives / Research Question	
Do you have funding for this study or are you requesting voluntary participation?	
Which of the following options best describes the study?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feasibility Study (only univariate counts of number of patients, e.g. number of patients with diabetes) • Cohort Characterisation Study (Report on patient characteristics, incidence/prevalence rates) • Prediction Study (Development and validation of a prediction model) • Population-level effect estimation Study (comparative safety or effectiveness study) • Other:
Which of the following data domains are needed for the study?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drugs • Conditions • Measurements • Observations • Devices • Procedures • Costs • Location • Provider

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Question	Details
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care site • Other:
What type of databases are requested?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hospital Databases • GP Databases • Registry Databases • Claims Databases • Other:
Do you already have data sources in mind based on the EHDEN Database Catalogue? If so, which?	
What is the minimum number of (additional) databases?	
What are the geographic requirements for your study?	
Select the requested services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contracting of Data Partners • Protocol Development • Project Management • Study Implementation • Study Execution • Study Report Writing • Scientific Publication Writing
If you already have a protocol (draft) please upload	
Do you have any additional questions or remarks?	
Can we share your information with potential Data Partners at this stage?	